

Nuclear Data Uncertainty Quantification of the Doppler Effect in the Southwest Experimental Fast Oxide Reactor Experiment

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ABSTRACT

The accuracy and predictive capability of neutronic calculation tools are essential for the development of advanced nuclear reactors, as they underpin design, safety, and optimization efforts. Their validation relies on high-quality experimental data, yet the scarcity of representative measurements—especially for fast-spectrum systems—remains a significant challenge. In this context, the historical SEFOR (Southwest Experimental Fast Oxide Reactor) experiments provide a unique and invaluable reference for validating sodium-cooled fast reactor analyses. This study presents a code-to-code validation including nuclear data uncertainty quantification of the Doppler effect in the SEFOR isothermal temperature rise experiment. The analysis focuses on SEFOR Core I-E, using both stochastic and deterministic approaches to assess the impact of nuclear data and modeling assumptions on reactivity and Doppler feedback coefficients. Monte Carlo codes TRIPOLI-4, Shift, and SERPENT were employed alongside deterministic solvers PERSENT (ARC suite) and APOLLO-3, each coupled with their respective nuclear data evaluations (ENDF/B-VII.0, VII.1, VIII.0, VIII.1, and JEFF3.1.1–4T3) and covariance matrices. Criticality and Doppler reactivity feedback effects were systematically compared across the codes to evaluate consistency, sensitivity profiles, and propagated uncertainties. Results indicate that discrepancies between ENDF and JEFF nuclear data libraries remain within expected uncertainty bounds, with ²³⁸U, ²³⁹Pu, and ¹⁶O identified as dominant contributors to the Doppler reactivity coefficient. Code-to-code comparisons show good agreement in both integral and energy-dependent sensitivity trends that confirm the applied modeling methodologies.

Keywords: SEFOR, Doppler effect, uncertainty quantification, nuclear data

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of advanced nuclear reactors strongly depends on the accuracy and predictive capability of neutronic calculation tools. These codes play a central role in the design, safety assessment, and optimization of reactor systems, where their ability to reliably capture key physical phenomena must be rigorously demonstrated. To ensure their credibility, extensive validation activities are performed, comparing computational predictions against high-quality experimental data obtained from dedicated facilities and benchmark programs.

Validation, however, critically depends on the availability and quality of experimental data. The limited number of representative experiments, particularly for fast-spectrum systems, poses a major challenge for current and future generations of reactor analysis tools. This scarcity emphasizes the enduring importance of historical experiments that were performed under well-characterized and thoroughly documented conditions. Among these, the Southwest Experimental Fast Oxide Reactor (SEFOR) [1] stands out as a unique experimental reference for sodium-cooled fast reactors.

SEFOR was specifically designed to study the dynamic and safety characteristics of fast reactors, providing an extensive dataset on reactivity coefficients, power distributions, and transient behavior.

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Its well-instrumented core allowed precise measurements of feedback mechanisms such as fuel expansion, coolant dilation, and spectral shifts [2] [3]. The pertinence of SEFOR extends beyond its historical role. Its experimental campaigns were conducted under conditions that closely resemble those expected in present and future fast reactor concepts, making it an invaluable source of information for uncertainty quantification and model verification. Under the auspice of the NEA WPRS, a SEFOR benchmark was proposed in order to provide a common framework for the validation and intercomparison of modern reactor physics codes and nuclear data evaluations in fast-spectrum conditions. The Isothermal Temperature Rise Test, in particular, provides a direct and controlled measurement of the overall temperature coefficient of reactivity, encompassing both Doppler and structural feedback effects [2]. In this paper we focus on this latter test performing a code-to-code comparison using modern calculation tools. This approach enables the evaluation of the consistency and sensitivity of different neutron physics codes and nuclear data libraries in predicting two key parameters: the criticality and the Doppler effect. Such comparisons contribute to identifying systematic discrepancies, assessing modeling assumptions, and improving confidence in simulation tools used for fast reactor analysis.

2. SEFOR ISOTHERMAL TEMPERATURE RISE

2.1. Core description

The Southwest Experimental Fast Oxide Reactor (SEFOR) was a sodium-cooled, pool-type fast reactor that operated in Fayetteville, Arkansas (USA). It was primarily designed to investigate the dynamic behavior and inherent safety features of liquid-sodium-cooled fast reactors providing an essential experimental foundation for studying reactivity coefficients, kinetics, and stability under both steady-state and transient conditions. The reactor core consisted of mixed uranium-plutonium oxide fuel with a nominal thermal power of about 20 MW. Throughout its experimental campaign, SEFOR conducted a wide range of isothermal, steady-state power tests and reactivity transients to study feedback mechanisms associated with Doppler Effect, fuel expansion, sodium thermal dilation, and spectral shifts. The resulting data provided invaluable insight into the intrinsic stability of fast reactors.

2.1.1. Isothermal temperature rise test

Among the steady-state experiments performed in SEFOR, the Isothermal Temperature Rise Test was carried out to determine the overall temperature coefficient of reactivity under well-controlled thermal conditions [2]. At the beginning of the core life, in Core I-E (see *Figure 1*), an isothermal temperature increase from 449 K to 677 K was performed while maintaining constant reactor power and coolant flow. The resulting change in reactivity was compensated by progressive insertion of the radial reflector segments as the temperature increased. This experiment provided a direct assessment of the combined feedback effects associated with Doppler Effect, fuel and structural expansion, sodium thermal dilation, and spectral shifts in the fast neutron spectrum and allowed determining the Doppler Effect and thermal expansion coefficients as depicted in Eq. 1. The measurements were performed, yielding uncertainties of 0.5¢ in reactivity and 0.5 K in core temperature for each reading.

$$dk(T_1 \rightarrow T_2) = \alpha * (T_2 - T_1) + k_D * \ln\left(\frac{T_2}{T_1}\right) \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. SEFOR core configuration I-E [2] (left) and Equation 1.

3. ANALYSIS ON THE SEFOR TEMPERATURE RISE

This Section provides the description of the codes, nuclear data and covariance matrices allowing to model the SEFOR Core I-E configuration. Rather than performing an experimental validation as in [4], in the present paper a code-to-code comparison in order to identify potential discrepancies, improving confidence in these tools.

3.1. Methods and codes

Three stochastic codes have been used in the present paper: TRIPOLI-4 [5], Shift [6] and SERPENT [8], from which TRIPOLI-4 and SERPENT are mainly used for criticality calculations while Shift has been used for both criticality and sensitivity calculations. To establish a reference state, k -eff was first computed for a cold isothermal case at 294 K. In this model, the sodium coolant was at temperature of 294 K, but its density was at 450 K. To quantify the Doppler effect, subsequent cases varied only the fuel temperature between 450 K and 677 K, while coolant conditions, geometry, and all other material densities were at their 450 K isothermal state values.

Shift is a Monte Carlo code developed at Oak Ridge National Laboratory. In Shift, sensitivity coefficients were evaluated using the iterated fission probability method. Each simulation used 500,000 neutron histories and 5,100 total cycles with 100 inactive cycles, yielding standard deviation of k -eff of ~ 1.5 pcm. Sensitivities were generated for 33 groups (to match PERSENT) and written to sensitivity data files (SDFs) for all isotopes and reactions. Uncertainties in the Doppler effect were then computed with the SCALE/TSAR sequence [7] using the paired SDFs (fuel temperatures at 450 K and 677 K) generated with the same nuclear data library together with the corresponding covariance data. The following libraries were considered: ENDF/B-VII.0, ENDF/B-VII.1 and ENDF/B-VIII.0 [9]. Covariance data were taken from the associated SCALE releases [7]: 44-group for ENDF/B-VII.0, and 56-group for ENDF/B-VII.1 and ENDF/B-VIII.0.

Two deterministic codes have been used in order to obtain the Doppler reactivity feedback sensitivities well as its uncertainties: PERSENT [10] and APOLLO3. In particular, PERSENT (PERTurbation and SENSitivity for Transport) is developed at Argonne National Laboratory based on the perturbation theory to calculate reactivities and its sensitivity coefficients. Its function was also expanded to include calculations for reactivity feedback coefficients based on the generalized perturbation theory and estimate uncertainties for a given response due to uncertainties in nuclear cross section data. The method typically requires calculations of both the perturbed and unperturbed forward and adjoint fluxes. PERSENT links the DIF3D-VARIANT [11] nodal solver in the Argonne Reactor Computation Code (ARC) suite [12] to perform the 3-D full core calculations. For modeling Core I-E, the reactor lattice physics code MC²-3 [13] was used to generate 33- energy-group cross sections for calculating the full core fluxes. Although MC²-3 can use both ENDF/B-VII.0 [14] and ENDF/B-VII.1 [15] libraries to generate coarse energy group cross sections, the ENDF/B-VII.0 library was used for modeling Core I-E and the co-variance matrix COMMARA-2.0 [16] which was based on ENDF/B-VII.0 was used for estimating uncertainties in the calculated criticalities. To calculate the sensitivity coefficients as well as the estimated uncertainties in the Doppler effects due to cross section uncertainties, the 33-g cross sections at 450 K which was used in the full core calculation was perturbed by cross sections generated with temperatures at 677 K.

Similarly, APOLLO3 [17] relies on a lattice calculation through the TDT-CPM and TDT-MOC [18] solvers, that enable to generate effective cross sections (i.e. homogenized and energy-condensed). The effective cross sections are then used by the MINARET [19] solver, which is a discrete ordinates calculation solver. The core description in MINARET considers a heterogeneous description of fuel pellets and 33 energy group energetic mesh. Sensitivities are then calculated through the generalized perturbation theory requiring calculations of both the perturbed and unperturbed forward and adjoint fluxes. Finally, the COMAC-V1 [20] covariance matrix is used allowing to estimate uncertainties either on the criticality or the Doppler Effect. Calculations using TRIPOLI-4 and APOLLO-3 use JEFF nuclear data libraries [21] [22] [23] as depicted in *Table I*, which summarizes the used calculations tools for the presented results in next Chapter

Table I. Calculation codes and nuclear libraries.

Institute		Calculation code	Nuclear data	Covariance matrix
ANL	Stochastic	SERPENT	ENDF/B-VII.1	
	Deterministic	ARC		COMARRA-2.0
CEA	Stochastic	TRIPOLI-4	JEFF3.1.1, JEFF3.2, JEFF3.3, JEFF4T3	COMAC-V1
	Deterministic	APOLLO-3		
ORNL	Stochastic	Shift	ENDF/B-VII.0, ENDF/B-VII.1, ENDF/B-VIII.0, ENDF/B-VIII.1	SCALE cov. lib. based on the corresponding ENDF/B

3.2. Results

The criticality results are presented in Table II along with the mean and standard deviation and the statistical uncertainty of the calculations. Differences in k_{eff} between the JEFF nuclear data evaluations reach up to 500 pcm, while those obtained with ENDF can be as large as 1000 pcm. As a result, the standard deviation of the ENDF-based calculations is approximately twice that derived from JEFF. These discrepancies should be interpreted in the context of nuclear data uncertainties, which, for the JEFF-3.1.1 evaluation, have been estimated using the COMAC-V1 covariance data, yielding an uncertainty of about 700 pcm. This uncertainty is about 800 pcm for the ENDF/B-VII.0 library with the COMARRA-2.0 covariance matrix. These results indicate that the observed differences between JEFF and ENDF calculations are consistent with the expected range of nuclear data uncertainties.

The results regarding the Fuel Doppler Effect are provided in Table III. The observed discrepancies between JEFF and ENDF libraries are in agreement since it is contained within the statistical uncertainty at 2σ . Sensitivity analysis is performed in order to identify the main isotopic contributors to the Doppler reactivity coefficient and quantify their relative impact on the overall uncertainty.

Table II. Criticality results

Calculation code	Nuclear data	k_{eff}	μ	σ	$U_{stat} (1\sigma)$
SERPENT	ENDF/B-VII.1	1.01481	-	-	<3E-5
TRIPOLI-4	JEFF3.1.1	1.01936	1.017045	0.00257	<3E-5
	JEFF3.2	1.01411			
	JEFF3.3	1.01905			
	JEFF4T3	1.01566			
	JENDL4	1.02316	-	-	
Shift	ENDF/B-VII.0	1.02020	1.01399	0.00502	<4E-5
	ENDF/B-VII.1	1.01586			
	ENDF/B-VIII.0	1.01075			
	ENDF/B-VIII.1	1.00916			

Table III. Doppler Effect results

Calculation code	Nuclear data	$K_D \text{ Fuel } (\%)$	μ	σ	$U_{stat} (1\sigma)$
SERPENT	ENDF/B-VII.1	-278.5	-	-	3.06
TRIPOLI-4	JEFF3.1.1	-266.6	-269.0	5.93	~4.57
	JEFF3.2	-269.8			
	JEFF3.3	-276.8			
	JEFF4T3	-262.8			
	JENDL4	-278.7	-	-	
Shift	ENDF/B-VII.0	-271.6	-272.8	2.48	~4.22
	ENDF/B-VII.1	-275.4			
	ENDF/B-VIII.0	-270.0			
	ENDF/B-VIII.1	-274.4			

Integrated sensitivities on the Doppler Effect are provided in *Figure 2*. The results indicate that ^{239}Pu , ^{16}O and ^{238}U dominate this effect, with secondary contributions from ^{23}Na , ^9Be and ^{56}Fe . Overall, the integrated sensitivity coefficients agree well among the three codes. However, it is noticed that the integrated sensitivity coefficients for the fission spectrum of ^{239}Pu and ^{238}U calculated by Shift with ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data are negligible with large uncertainties compared to the other two codes.

Figure 2. Integrated sensitivities on the Doppler Effect using APOLLO-3 and JEFF3.1.1, PERSENT and ENDF/B-VII.1. and Shift and ENDF/B-VII.1.

Profile sensitivities of the Doppler effect are now compared between codes, using Shift, APOLLO-3, and ARC/PERSENT. All calculations were performed using 33 energy groups, additionally APOLLO-3 considered 160 energy groups as shown in *Figure 3*. Overall, there is good consistency on sensitivity profiles between calculations with common trends along the energy spectrum. Secondly, as expected, fine sensitivity profiles provide a finer resolution of the energy distribution, leading to slight differences in the maximum and minimum sensitivity values. The 33-group profile shows good overall agreement with the 160-group results; however, some local sensitivity dips observed in the finer energy structure are not captured in the coarser discretization. This is particularly evident for reactions such as $^{239}\text{Pu}(n, f)$ and $^{16}\text{O}(n, n)$. Finally, the calculated sensitivity profile of elastic scattering of ^{16}O by Shift shows slightly stronger fluctuations than those obtained with the other codes, which can be attributed to the lower statistical precision inherent to Monte Carlo simulations.

Nuclear data uncertainties were then calculated using the corresponding covariance matrices, as summarized in *Figure 4*. The estimated uncertainties range from 2.0% to 3.75%, depending on the specific nuclear data and covariance matrix employed. The JEFF3.1.1 uncertainty is mostly dominated by ^{238}U reactions, and in most of the cases $^{238}\text{U} (n, n')$ is the main contributor to the uncertainty, except in the ENDF/B-VIII.0. For this latter it is the ^{239}Pu and ^{23}Na isotopes that contribute the most. The observed discrepancies between ARC/PERSENT and Shift when using ENDF/B-VII.1 are attributed to the different nature of the reactor physics modeling (i.e. deterministic vs Monte Carlo), and the choice of covariance matrix. Besides, as shown in *Figure 2*, the integrated sensitivities generated by Shift have larger statistical uncertainties for elastic scattering and for the fission spectrum that can propagate to a larger uncertainty in the Doppler effect.

Figure 3. Energy sensitivity profiles of most sensitive reactions of the Doppler effect.

Figure 4. Nuclear data uncertainties calculated with APOLLO-3, PERSENT and SHIFT.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The design of new nuclear systems necessitates predictive simulation capabilities, requiring models to move beyond data reproduction and anticipate reactor behavior under novel conditions. Achieving such reliability requires a coherent validation framework grounded in the highest quality experimental benchmarks. In this context, SEFOR remains an essential reference, providing uniquely detailed measurements of reactivity feedbacks and temperature effects that are crucial for the qualification of modern analysis tools.

This study performed a detailed uncertainty quantification analysis of the Doppler effect in the SEFOR isothermal temperature rise experiment using multiple modern reactor physics tools. Despite methodological and nuclear data differences, all calculations exhibited consistent predictions of reactivity and Doppler feedback within the uncertainty range of 2–4%. Sensitivity analyses identified ^{239}Pu , ^{238}U , and ^{16}O as the leading contributors to uncertainty. Moreover, the uncertainty quantification resulted in similar contributors, ^{239}Pu , ^{238}U , and ^{16}O with ^{56}Fe and ^{23}Na as secondary contributors.

Overall, the stochastic (Shift, SERPENT, TRIPOLI-4) and deterministic (PERSENT, APOLLO-3) methods codes show an excellent agreement. The SEFOR benchmark continues to serve as a valuable reference for nuclear data validation, code verification, and the quantification of reactivity feedback uncertainties relevant to sodium-cooled fast reactors. Future work will extend this framework to additional SEFOR configurations, namely for Core II configuration for which the neutron spectrum is hardened. Secondly, recent nuclear data as JEFF 4.0 will also be included in further analysis, and a reference methodology for uncertainty quantification (as the total Monte Carlo method) will also be included.

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